

Mapply: When You Need to Iterate Over Multiple Inputs

Dr. Mowinckel

2025-10-01

In an [older post](#), I showed the basics of replacing loops with apply functions. I briefly touched on `mapply` at the end, but it deserves its own explanation because it's incredibly useful once you understand when to reach for it.

The key difference: `sapply` works with one varying input, `mapply` works with multiple varying inputs that need to be paired up.

When `sapply` isn't enough

Let's start with a scenario where `sapply` works fine, then see where it breaks down.

Say we want to generate some random samples with different sample sizes:

```
sample_sizes <- c(10, 20, 15, 30)
samples <- sapply(
  sample_sizes,
  function(n) rnorm(n, mean = 0, sd = 1),
  simplify = FALSE
)

# Look at the lengths
sapply(samples, length)
```

```
[1] 10 20 15 30
```

This works because we're only varying one thing: the sample size. The mean and sd stay constant.

But what if we want different means for each sample?

```

sample_sizes <- c(10, 20, 15, 30)
means <- c(5, 10, 7, 12)

# This won't work as intended
samples <- sapply(sample_sizes, function(n) rnorm(n, mean = ???, sd = 1))
sapply(samples, mean)

```

We're stuck. `sapply` can only iterate over one vector at a time.

Enter mapply

`mapply` is designed exactly for this situation - when you need to pair up multiple vectors element-wise:

```

generate_samples <- function(n, mean_val) {
  rnorm(n, mean = mean_val, sd = 1)
}

sample_sizes <- c(10, 20, 15, 30)
means <- c(5, 10, 7, 12)

samples <- mapply(
  generate_samples,
  n = sample_sizes,
  mean_val = means,
  SIMPLIFY = FALSE
)

# Check the means of our samples
sapply(samples, mean)

```

```
[1] 5.112995 9.896735 6.904238 12.074860
```

Perfect! The first sample has ~10 observations with mean ~5, the second has ~20 observations with mean ~10, and so on. An important thing with `mapply` is that the vectors you pass in must be the same length, as they are paired element-wise. It will recycle shorter vectors, but that can lead to unexpected results if you're not careful.

```
# Only 2 means for 4 sizes
short_means <- c(5, 10)
samples <- mapply(
  generate_samples,
  n = sample_sizes,
  mean_val = short_means,
  SIMPLIFY = FALSE
)
sapply(samples, mean)
```

```
[1] 4.880864 9.393517 5.050365 10.164239
```

You can see that the means are recycled, which may not be what you want. So it's best to add a check to ensure your vectors are the same length before using `mapply`, if you are getting inputs from elsewhere.

```
if (length(sample_sizes) != length(means)) {
  stop("sample_sizes and means must be the same length")
}
```

A more complex example: Scaling data

Let's work with something more realistic. Say we have test scores from different classes, and we want to standardize each class separately, but with different target means and standard deviations.

```
# Create some test data
set.seed(42)
class_a <- rnorm(25, mean = 75, sd = 10)
class_b <- rnorm(30, mean = 82, sd = 8)
class_c <- rnorm(20, mean = 78, sd = 12)

scores <- list(class_a, class_b, class_c)
class_names <- c("Math", "Science", "English")
scores
```

```
[[1]]
 [1] 88.70958 69.35302 78.63128 81.32863 79.04268 73.93875 90.11522 74.05341
 [9] 95.18424 74.37286 88.04870 97.86645 61.11139 72.21211 73.66679 81.35950
[17] 72.15747 48.43545 50.59533 88.20113 71.93361 57.18692 73.28083 87.14675
```

```
[25] 93.95193
```

```
[[2]]
```

```
[1] 78.55625 79.94184 67.89470 85.68078 76.88004 85.64360 87.63870 90.28083  
[9] 77.12859 86.03964 68.26393 75.72433 75.19274 62.68634 82.28898 83.64799  
[17] 79.11154 88.06531 76.18636 71.05375 85.46254 75.50885 93.55281 78.54843  
[25] 87.24518 84.57540 75.72929 94.60582 87.14319 82.71809
```

```
[[3]]
```

```
[1] 81.31861 86.15147 79.07799 42.08292 81.41860 73.59318 80.22277 84.98188  
[9] 94.79684 69.27250 93.63051 82.03018 90.46207 89.04874 86.65054 65.48257  
[17] 76.91776 85.48222 66.55772 71.48605
```

```
# Look at original means and sds  
sapply(scores, mean)
```

```
[1] 76.87536 80.76653 79.03326
```

```
sapply(scores, sd)
```

```
[1] 13.063647 7.590105 12.118638
```

Now let's say we want to rescale each class to have specific target means and standard deviations:

```
# Math=80, Science=85, English=75  
target_means <- c(80, 85, 75)  
  
# Different spreads for each subject  
target_sds <- c(5, 8, 10)
```

Here's the scaling function:

```
rescale_scores <- function(scores, target_mean, target_sd) {  
  # Standardize to mean=0, sd=1  
  standardized <- (scores - mean(scores)) / sd(scores)  
  standardized * target_sd + target_mean  
}
```

Using a loop would mean using a counter to index each vector, and would look like this:

```

rescaled_scores <- list()
for (i in seq_along(scores)) {
  rescaled_scores[[i]] <- rescale_scores(
    scores[[i]],
    target_means[i],
    target_sds[i]
  )
}

```

I'll be honest, this isn't too bad. I've done it plenty of times, especially when the logic is more complex. But once I got more comfortable creating my own functions, I found `mapply` to be a cleaner solution. With `mapply`, we can do this cleanly without indexing:

```

rescaled_scores <- mapply(
  rescale_scores, # the function you want to apply
  scores = scores, # The varying inputs
  target_mean = target_means,
  target_sd = target_sds,
  SIMPLIFY = FALSE # to keep the output as a list
)

# Check our results
sapply(rescaled_scores, mean)

```

```
[1] 80 85 75
```

```
sapply(rescaled_scores, sd)
```

```
[1] 5 8 10
```

Exactly what we wanted! No indexing, no temporary variables. It really is a very clean solution. Another nice thing about it is that since we are not relying in indexing, we can easily change the order of our inputs without breaking anything.

Adding more arguments

What if we also want to add class identifiers? We can add more vectors to match:

```

rescale_and_label <- function(scores, target_mean, target_sd, class_name) {
  rescaled <- rescale_scores(scores, target_mean, target_sd)
  data.frame(
    score = rescaled,
    class = class_name,
    student_id = seq_along(rescaled)
  )
}

result_data <- mapply(
  rescale_and_label,
  scores = scores,
  target_mean = target_means,
  target_sd = target_sds,
  class_name = class_names,
  SIMPLIFY = FALSE
)

# Combine into one data.frame
final_data <- do.call(rbind, result_data)
head(final_data)

```

	score	class	student_id
1	84.52945	Math	1
2	77.12089	Math	2
3	80.67206	Math	3
4	81.70445	Math	4
5	80.82952	Math	5
6	78.87604	Math	6

When you have some constant arguments

Sometimes you have multiple varying inputs AND some constant ones. That's where `MoreArgs` comes in, which lets you pass a list of constant arguments to your function. This now becomes very powerful.

```

rescale_with_bounds <- function(
  scores,
  target_mean,
  target_sd,
  min_score,

```

```

max_score
) {
  rescaled <- rescale_scores(scores, target_mean, target_sd)
  # Apply bounds
  pmax(min_score, pmin(max_score, rescaled))
}

# All classes have same score bounds
bounded_scores <- mapply(
  rescale_with_bounds,
  scores = scores,
  target_mean = target_means,
  target_sd = target_sds,
  MoreArgs = list(
    min_score = 0,
    max_score = 100
  ),
  SIMPLIFY = FALSE
)

# Check that we don't exceed bounds
sapply(bounded_scores, function(x) c(min = min(x), max = max(x)))

```

```

      [,1]      [,2]      [,3]
min 69.11486 65.94341 44.50950
max 88.03416 99.58667 88.00772

```

That's it! You can mix and match varying and constant arguments easily.

The mapply pattern

I find mapply most useful for:

1. **Simulation studies** - varying multiple parameters simultaneously
2. **Data processing** - when different groups need different treatments
3. **Modeling** - fitting the same model type with different parameters

The pattern is always:

1. Write a function that takes multiple arguments
2. Create vectors for each varying argument (same length)
3. Use `mapply` to pair them up
4. Add any constant arguments via `MoreArgs`

Tidyverse equivalent

For completeness, the `purrr` equivalent uses `pmap`, which stands for “parallel map”. A map is a function that applies a function to each element of a list or vector, so acts like `lapply` or `sapply`. The name “map” comes from other functional programming languages, and is therefore a name for this same concept that is more widely used outside of R. In `purrr`, there are several types of map functions, which also validates the output type (e.g. `map_dbl` for numeric output, `map_chr` for character output, etc.). The standard `map` function returns a list, like `lapply`.

As noted in the `purrr` documentation, “parallel” here does not refer to parallel computing, but rather that multiple inputs are processed together. To use `pmap`, you need to put your varying inputs into a list, and in standard tidyverse fashion, the input is the first argument (contrary to the applies where it is further down the argument tree).

```
library(purrr)

result_data <- list(
  scores = scores,
  target_mean = target_means,
  target_sd = target_sds,
  class_name = class_names
) |>
  pmap(rescale_and_label)
result_data
```

```
[[1]]
  score class student_id
1 84.52945 Math          1
2 77.12089 Math          2
3 80.67206 Math          3
4 81.70445 Math          4
5 80.82952 Math          5
6 78.87604 Math          6
```

7	85.06744	Math	7
8	78.91992	Math	8
9	87.00757	Math	9
10	79.04219	Math	10
11	84.27650	Math	11
12	88.03416	Math	12
13	73.96647	Math	13
14	78.21518	Math	14
15	78.77195	Math	15
16	81.71627	Math	16
17	78.19427	Math	17
18	69.11486	Math	18
19	69.94154	Math	19
20	84.33484	Math	20
21	78.10859	Math	21
22	72.46441	Math	22
23	78.62422	Math	23
24	83.93129	Math	24
25	86.53591	Math	25

[[2]]

	score	class	student_id
1	82.67036	Science	1
2	84.13078	Science	2
3	71.43304	Science	3
4	90.17964	Science	4
5	80.90363	Science	5
6	90.14045	Science	6
7	92.24329	Science	7
8	95.02811	Science	8
9	81.16560	Science	9
10	90.55788	Science	10
11	71.82221	Science	11
12	79.68550	Science	12
13	79.12521	Science	13
14	65.94341	Science	14
15	86.60467	Science	15
16	88.03707	Science	16
17	83.25564	Science	17
18	92.69294	Science	18
19	80.17249	Science	19
20	74.76270	Science	20
21	89.94962	Science	21

```
22 79.45839 Science      22
23 98.47679 Science      23
24 82.66212 Science      24
25 91.82853 Science      25
26 89.01457 Science      26
27 79.69073 Science      27
28 99.58667 Science      28
29 91.72103 Science      29
30 87.05695 Science      30
```

```
[[3]]
```

```
      score  class student_id
1  76.88582 English         1
2  80.87377 English         2
3  75.03692 English         3
4  44.50950 English         4
5  76.96832 English         5
6  70.51099 English         6
7  75.98155 English         7
8  79.90866 English         8
9  88.00772 English         9
10 66.94566 English        10
11 87.04529 English        11
12 77.47298 English        12
13 84.43078 English        13
14 83.26453 English        14
15 81.28559 English        15
16 63.81831 English        16
17 73.25435 English        17
18 80.32152 English        18
19 64.70550 English        19
20 68.77224 English        20
```

Several things about `pmap` that I like a lot when I don't have to worry about dependencies:

1. The input is the first argument, which I find more intuitive.
2. You can use the pipe operator to build up your inputs, which I find makes it easier to read.
3. You can use anonymous functions with the `~` syntax, which I find cleaner for short functions.

4. Additional constant arguments can be passed directly in the `pmap` call, without needing a separate `MoreArgs` list.
5. You can toggle progress bars with the `.progress` argument, which is nice for long-running tasks.
6. You can [easily add parallel processing](#) using the `{mirai}` package.

Base R `mapply` keeps your dependencies minimal and works everywhere, if that is a concern. But if you are already using the tidyverse, `pmap` is a great alternative, and in my opinion, is more readable.

Wrapping up

Think of `mapply` as the tool for when you need to “zip” multiple vectors together and apply a function to each matched set. If you find yourself writing loops where you’re indexing into multiple vectors with the same `i`, that’s usually a sign that `mapply` would be cleaner.